

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND IR DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Media of isolation	% of Carbon		% of Hydrogen		% of Metal		Shifting of band in complex from ir band of ligand*
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
Cu(C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₂) ₂	Ethanolic	54.35	54.32	8.60	8.41	14.39	14.50	-3700(s) ^φ -disappear [§]
Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₂) ₂	Ethanolic	54.95	54.86	8.70	8.69	13.44	13.21	3550wb disappear
Bi(C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₂) ₂ NO ₃ ·2H ₂ O	Ethanolic	39.03	38.43	6.00	6.00	32.96	32.85	3710ms disappear
VO ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₂) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Aqueous-Ethanolic	52.03	52.19	8.31	8.31	11.05	11.39	disappear
Pd(C ₁₀ H ₁₉ O ₂) ₂	-do-	51.49	51.62	8.21	8.21	22.75	22.61	disappear 1790wb

* ir band of ligand - band pertaining to ^φ-OH is 3600 cm⁻¹ ;
[§]-CHO is 1760 cm⁻¹.

Spectrophotometric studies were carried out by molar ratio method⁶ and Job's continuous variation method. The optical density fixed for complexes is shown in Table 1. The complexes obey Beer's law under the concentration range 1 × 10⁻³ M to 5 × 10⁻² M.

The ir spectra (Table 2) reveals that various bands assigned to the donor molecules of the ligand⁹ have shifted either to lower frequency region or higher frequency region. The shift of these bands show coordination of this ligand with metals. Elemental analysis of the complexes further confirms 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the ligand as well as structure of the complexes. The complexes are found to be insoluble in most of the common organic solvents like acetone, methanol, ether, benzene and chloroform etc. Their melting points are also given.

Thus from electrometric and analytical data complexes were found to have the following structure :

Here M = Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Bi³⁺, Co²⁺, VO₂³⁺ and Pd²⁺

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Mixed Ligand Anionic Complexes of Copper(II)

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STUDY of literatures reveals the preparation¹⁻⁷ of a large number of tetrahalo complexes of the type [L]₂ [MX₄] where L = tetraalkylammonium halide or pseudo halide. Although, Bonamico and Dessy⁸ have synthesised anionic tetraalkylammonium tetrachloro cuprate(II) complexes which contain discrete distorted tetrahedral [CuCl₄]²⁻ ions, little

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TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND ELECTRONIC DATA

Complexes	%Copper		%Chloride		%Nitrogen		Λ_m mhos cm^2	μ_{eff} B.M.	ν_{max} kK
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.			
$[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4(\nu\text{-Pic})_2]$	13.86	13.95	31.04	31.13	12.20	12.29	225	1.85	13,900
$[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4\text{Py}_2]$	14.81	14.87	33.07	33.17	12.94	13.10	240	1.80	14,500
$[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4\text{DM}_2]$	17.59	17.68	39.36	39.45	15.42	15.58	220	1.85	13,800
$[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4\text{An}_2]$	13.87	13.95	31.02	31.13	12.16	12.29	235	1.82	15,200
$[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4\text{Q}_2]$	12.43	12.50	26.71	26.88	10.50	10.62	222	1.82	15,200
$[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4\text{P}_2]$	14.41	14.46	32.12	32.26	12.62	12.75	245	1.75	16,000
$[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4\text{PH}]$	14.08	14.15	31.43	31.55	12.34	12.47	240	1.70	14,500
$[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4\text{BP}]$	14.88	14.94	33.20	33.33	13.02	13.16	220	1.80	13,800
$[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4\text{en}]$	19.22	19.30	42.88	43.04	16.88	17.00	225	1.75	14,000
$[\text{L}][\text{CuCl}_4\text{Qn}]$	18.39	18.43	30.73	30.83	8.00	8.12	195	2.05	13,600; 21,000
$[\text{L}][\text{CuCl}_4\text{M}]$	21.92	22.00	36.69	36.81	9.54	9.69	120	1.95	13,500; 21,500

L=monomethylammonium cation; $\nu\text{-Pic}$ = ν -Picoline; An=Aniline; PH=1,10-Phenanthroline; ^2Py =Pyridine; Q=Quinoline; BP=2,2'-Bipyridine; en=Ethylenediamine; DM=Dimethylamine; P=Piperidine; Qn=Quinaldine; M=Morpholine.

work is done to change the stereochemistry of these complexes by reacting with other nitrogen, oxygen or sulphur donor ligands. The nature of cation can influence the coordination number of the metal in anionic complex. The present communication describes the preparation and characterization of some tetra- and hexa-coordinated mixed ligand anionic copper(II) complexes using monomethyl ammonium cation and various mono- and bidentate nitrogen donor heterocyclic bases.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. An ethanolic solution of copper(II) chloride was treated with an ethanolic solution of monomethyl ammonium chloride in 1 : 2 proportion when golden yellow compound of bis(monomethyl ammonium) tetrachloro cuprate(II) was separated out. This was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

The mixed ligand complexes were prepared by adding requisite amount (1 : 2 ratio) of ligands separately to ethanolic suspension of bis(monomethylammonium) tetrachloro cuprate(II) and refluxing for about 30 to 45 minutes. On cooling, crystalline compounds separated out which were then filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Metal and chloride in the complexes were determined by complexometric EDTA titration method and nitrogen by micro-analysis. Usual techniques² were employed for measurements of molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, ir spectra and electronic spectra. X-ray powder photograph of two complexes were also recorded.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of analysis and conductance data, the complexes have the composition $[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4\text{B}_2]$, $[\text{L}]_2[\text{CuCl}_4\text{B}']$ and $[\text{L}][\text{CuCl}_4\text{B}'']$, where B= ν -picoline, pyridine, quinoline, piperidine, aniline,

dimethylamine; B'=1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridine ethylenediamine; B''=quinaldine and morpholine. The first two categories of complexes are blue, green and shiny black in colour and are 2 : 1 electrolytes as indicated by their conductance values (Table 1). The third category of compounds are brown to greenish yellow in colour and are 1 : 1 electrolytes. The observed magnetic moments of these complexes lie in the range of 1.70 to 2.05 BM normally expected for copper(II) complexes^{10,11}.

In the ir spectra absorption bands are noticed at 920(ν_{as}), 1000(ν_{s}), 1250(ν_{as}), 1405(ν_{s}), 1490(ν_{s}) and 3050(ν_{as}), cm^{-1} characteristic of the bands due to monomethylammonium ion, modified due to complexation. Most of the absorption bands due to free nitrogen donor ligands have been modified in the anionic complexes indicating their coordination copper(II) ion. Evidence for the bonding of these heterocyclic nitrogen donors have been further substantiated by appearance of bands $\sim 350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ion frequency region assignable¹² to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$. In addition, absorption band $\sim 220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be attributed to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ vibration.

All the complexes except those with quinaldine and morpholine show an electronic spectral band in the region 13,800-16,000 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to the transition $2E_g \rightarrow 2T_{2g}$ characteristic of distorted octahedral copper(II) complexes¹³. For a truly tetrahedral copper(II) complexes, crystal field theory predicts one transition $2T_2 \rightarrow 2E$. Sacconi and Ciampoline, however, studying the electronic spectra of a salicyledaminato copper(II) complex suggested that flattening of the tetrahedral results in the splitting of both ground and excited levels, so that four transitions are expected. A truly tetrahedral compound should exhibit¹⁴ one broad band below 10,000 cm^{-1} , but they obtained bands at 8,500, 13,600 and 21,000 cm^{-1} and predicted a pseudo-tetrahedral configuration for their compounds. In the spectra of quinaldine and morpholine complexes now reported, the bands below 10,000 cm^{-1} could not be recorded on the instrument used but other two bands near the same

regions reported by Sacconi *et al* were obtained. Hence, these two compounds have a pseudo-tetrahedral configuration in conformity with the earlier observations⁸.

The X-ray powder photograph of the two complexes $[L]_2$, $[CuCl_4(\nu\text{-pic})_2]$ and $[L]_2[CuCl_4(An)_2]$ have been studied. The grazing angle (θ) and the lattice spacing value (d) have been calculated. This study indicates that the two complexes belong to the cubic system having the unit cell dimensions of 3.079 Å and 3.200 Å respectively.

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Studies of Cation Exchange Behaviour of Magnesium Trisilicate

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MAGNESIUM trisilicate (MTS) has been used for chromatographic separation of organic compounds by several workers¹⁻⁵. No attempt has, however, been made to study the sorption behaviour of inorganic ions using MTS. The present study reports the sorption behaviour of MTS, under static conditions, using some metal complexes of identical formal charge but differing in size and shape such as ammine complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II).

Experimental

Magnesium trisilicate (MTS): It was obtained from E. Merck and treated with 2N HCl for 24 hrs to remove any soluble impurity. The free HCl was removed by washing with water. Finally, it was dried at 100° for 14 hrs and stored in a desiccator.

The ammine complexes were prepared by dissolving appropriate quantities of individual metal sulphate in aqueous ammonia containing ammonium sulphate (buffer). All experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 3^\circ$.

Determination of the amounts of the metal complexes sorbed: 0.5 gm of MTS was mixed with 25 ml of a sample of metal complex solution of specific composition and pH value. After shaking for three hrs (sufficient to reach equilibrium), the solid was separated by centrifuge. 5 ml of portions of aliquot were analysed for the metal ions complexometrically⁶. The difference in the metal concentration before and after sorption corresponded to the amount of the metal complex retained on MTS. The distribution coefficient (Kd) and selectivity quotients were determined using the formulae reported earlier^{7,8}.

Results and Discussion

The results presented in Tables 1 and 2 bring out the following interesting points:

1. The q_0 values increase with increasing concentration of metal solutions up to a certain concentration (0.05M) and then decrease (Table 1). The Kd values decrease with increase of concentration.
2. Zn(II) has maximum sorption of all the metal complexes studied (Table 1).
3. In general, selectivity quotients are adversely affected by an increase in the concentration of the exchanging ion (Table 2).